

Establishing design strategies for emissive materials with inverted singlet-triplet energy gap (INVEST): A computational perspective on how symmetry rules the interplay between triplet harvesting and light emission

Gaetano Ricci^a, Juan-Carlos Sancho-García^b and Yoann Olivier^{*a}

^aLaboratory for Computational Modeling of Functional Materials,
Namur Institute of Structured Matter, E-mail: yoann.olivier@unamur.be
Université de Namur, Rue de Bruxelles, 61, B-5000 Namur, Belgium

^bDepartment of Physical Chemistry,
University of Alicante,
E-03080 Alicante, Spain

Abstract

The inversion of the lowest singlet and triplet excited state energy gap, in fully organic triangle-based compounds, can give rise to a new exergonic pathway to enhance the Organic Light Emitting Diodes (OLEDs) performance, going beyond the novel yet promising Thermally Activated Delayed Fluorescence (TADF) mechanism. If, on one hand, the origin of this inversion, arising from the interplay between exchange and electron correlation effects, has been extensively investigated in last years, identifying the *wavefunction* methods as key to predict the excited-state inversion, on the other hand a proper picture of the structure-property relationships characterizing these systems is still missing. In this work, we thus assess the effect of different symmetry point groups (D_{3h} , C_{2v} , C_{3h} and C_{3v}) on the orbital localization to shed light on the role that the symmetry has in determining the optical features of the triangulene systems (on both S_1 - T_1 inversion and oscillator strengths). The presence of the C_2 axis and the σ_v plane (as it happens for the D_{3h} , C_{2v} and C_{3v} groups) turned out to be critical for ensuring the proper orbital localization aimed at minimizing the exchange interaction and therefore favouring the inversion. In particular, adopting a C_{2v} (and its subgroups) symmetry, either through the proper doping pattern, by introducing substituents, or by merging two triangulene cores, is the only way to conciliate a negative ΔE_{ST} and a non-zero oscillator strength. Finally, we gathered the lessons learnt from this analysis to establish a series of design rules, aimed at helping the identification of inverted singlet-triplet (INVEST) emitters for applications in the next generation of OLEDs.

1 Introduction

Acclaimed for their brightness, lightness, as well as their potential flexibility and easy processability, Organic Light-Emitting Diodes (OLEDs) are representing an established technology in devices such as smartphones and TVs, or lighting applications, to name just a few of them. If, on one hand, these features make OLEDs more attractive than their inorganic counterpart, on the other hand the pure organic nature of these emitters severely limits the internal quantum efficiency (IQE); i.e., the ratio between the number of photons emitted upon charge injection. Indeed, in an OLED, light emission from an organic molecule takes place from the lowest singlet excited state (fluorescence) which results in a 25% IQE due to spin-statistics limit, the remaining 75% of triplet excitons decaying non-radiatively. Through the years, several design strategies have been conceived with the aim of fully harvesting both the singlet and the triplet excitons and foster IQEs beyond that 25% limit.

In the last years, a Thermally Activated Delayed Fluorescence (TADF) mechanism has represented a prominent solution to overcome the spin-statistics limit, relying on the minimization of the energy gap between the lowest singlet (S_1) and triplet (T_1) excited states, that is ΔE_{ST} ($= E(S_1) - E(T_1)$), to promote a thermally activated Reverse Intersystem Crossing (RISC) from the triplet to the singlet and reach, in theory, an IQE of ideally up to 100%. Because the ΔE_{ST} is known to be proportional to the hole-electron densities overlap, its minimization can be achieved by ensuring a spatial separation of the hole and electron densities. The initial design strategy of TADF emitters employs donor-acceptor compounds^[1-2], which thus guarantees the segregation of the hole and electron densities on different parts of the molecule thus prompting excited states with a high intramolecular Charge Transfer (intra-CT) character. However, this strategy suffers from two critical drawbacks: a broad emission and a small oscillator strength (emission cross-section, f_{osc}), both detrimental factors for the ultimate performance of a real-world OLED.

More recently, the Multi-Resonant TADF (MR-TADF) strategy proposed by Hatakeyama *et al.*^[3] solved this shortcoming through the synthesis of boron and/or nitrogen-doped organic materials such as DABNA-1 and TABNA (see Figure 1)^[4-10], in which complementary multiple resonance effects originating from the different heteroatoms turns into a localization of the highest-occupied molecular orbitals (HOMO) and lowest-unoccupied molecular orbitals (LUMO) on alternating atomic sites. The resulting short-range intra-CT guarantees a small ΔE_{ST} along with a narrow emission and a high oscillator strength.

Generally speaking, fully organic TADF molecular compounds which all display a closed-shell ground state electronic structure are expected to obey the analogue of the Hund's rule, which is generally assumed to lead to T_1 lying below S_1 , resulting in a

positive ΔE_{ST} , so that the harvesting of triplet excitons is driven by an up-conversion process.

Figure 1: chemical structure of DABNA-1, TABNA-1 and HAP-3TPA

Past experimental studies on two triangular shape compounds called cyclazine^[11] and triazacyclazine^[12], showed a close degeneracy of S_1 and T_1 along with a short lifetime of T_1 , features unusual for organic molecules. Besides those initial experimental observations, which are not fully conclusive, wavefunction-based quantum chemical calculations on these two molecules predicted a negative ΔE_{ST} , suggesting the potential inversion of the singlet and triplet energy order and the violation of the Hund's rule^[13]. The singlet-triplet inversion was indeed confirmed in 2019 by experimental investigations on another triangle shaped molecule called heptazine^[14], which provided no evidence of a triplet excited state below the lowest singlet excited state, feature again supported by wavefunction-based quantum chemical calculations resulting in a negative ΔE_{ST} .

Furthermore, those findings also help to understand a previous study (2013) by Adachi *et al.*^[21], who reported the synthesis of a heptazine derivative (HAP-3TPA) in which the strong acceptor power of the heptazine core (HAP) and the donor power of the three triarylamine (TPA) substituents induced an *intra*-CT character, leading to a $\Delta E_{ST} = 0.17$ eV in oxygen-free toluene solution. Employing the HAP-3TPA as emitter in an OLED device an EQE of 17.5% was reached. More intriguing, an unusual TADF behavior was observed in the solid state, i.e. a decrease of the TADF efficiency with an increase of the temperature, which suggested a thermally promoted endergonic intersystem crossing (ISC) and thus an inverted singlet-triplet energy order.

In our previous works^[13,16], we have investigated the electronic structure and the optical properties of a set of triangular shape compounds with different sizes and different doping patterns, either with nitrogen and/or boron atoms, by means of Time Dependent Density Functional Theory (TD-DFT) and *correlated wave function* methods. These studies confirmed the key role played by double and higher-order excitations as included in wave function-based methods, to promote the singlet-triplet inversion. Climbing the Jacob's ladder, Local Density Approximation (LDA), Generalized

Gradient Approximation (GGA) as well as hybrid functionals in combination with linear response TD-DFT are intrinsically unable to tackle the gap inversion because of the missing explicit description of double excitations. This problem can be solved when referring to double-hybrid functionals which includes a MP2-like correlation correction also extended to excited-state studies^[17]. However, the gap inversion we observed in the azaphenylene family is not systematically predicted for all double-hybrid functionals which precludes their black-box use for screening or designing new materials, and more investigations are still needed. Analogously, we carried out some tests employing the Spin-Flip TD-DFT method^[18,19] (SF-TD-DFT) (using a triplet state as a reference) for which the strong dependency on the chosen functional, along with the spin-contamination, precluded a systematic prediction of the negative ΔE_{ST} . Besides this, we identified in our past studies three features (at least) required to have the singlet-triplet inversion, each one being accurately quantifiable: i) low to moderate radicaloid character; ii) low exchange interaction; iii) large contribution of double excitations (generally $> 10\%$) to the S_1 and T_1 wave function, slightly higher for the former than for the latter.

The singlet-triplet inversion purely originates from electronic effects, namely from the interplay between the exchange interaction (Fermi correlation) acting on parallel spins and electron correlation (Coulomb correlation) interaction acting on anti-parallel spins. Whilst the former is a positive term promoting the stabilization of the triplet with respect to the singlet, the latter arises from the presence of doubly excited configurations (and/or higher order excitations) through wavefunction-based methodologies which introduce a stabilization of the singlet with respect to the triplet that, if large enough, can overcome the exchange interaction and provide a negative ΔE_{ST} ^[15]. However, these methodologies (and others in general) do not allow to disentangle the Coulomb correlation contribution from the exchange one.

Besides, it has been historically assumed that the singlet-triplet exchange interaction (K) was the only magnitude to control and/or tune, being proportional to the overlap between the orbitals involved in the electronic transition (ϕ_i and ϕ_a the occupied and unoccupied orbitals, respectively). Within the two-state model (e.g. a HOMO to LUMO transition) and assuming that S_1 and T_1 share the same electronic configuration, the magnitude of this interaction can be straightforwardly quantified through the Configuration Interaction Singles (CIS) calculations, leading to $\Delta E_{ST}=2K$ ^[13-15]. That is, the smaller is the HOMO-LUMO overlap, the smaller is the exchange interaction, significantly reducing the singlet-triplet gap. As a first guess on the magnitude of the exchange integral, it follows that the (even visual or qualitative) evaluation of the shape and localization of the molecular orbitals involved in the description of the excited states can guide the minimization of ΔE_{ST} in triangulene compounds, potentially leading to singlet-triplet inversion. Previously, computational studies on the potential

inversion of the singlet-triplet energy order in small conjugated hydrocarbon systems such as propylene, pentalene and heptalene pointed out on the impact of the symmetry point group variation on the orbital pattern and its effect in modulating the ΔE_{ST} from a positive to a negative value^[20].

The triangulene compounds showing a negative ΔE_{ST} are characterized by the typical hole-electron pattern of the MR-TADF compounds; i.e., an alternating distribution of hole and electron densities on adjacent atomic sites so that the nature of the lower-lying singlet and triplet excited states typically displays a short-range charge transfer character. This picture is also consistent with the spatial distribution of the molecular orbitals: taking cyclazine as example, the HOMO and LUMO are mainly localized on alternating atomic sites, favoring the minimization of their overlap (see Fig.1a and Fig.2a). This orbital distribution is dictated by the symmetry of the bare triangulene core with the most promising compounds belonging to the D_{3h} symmetry point group^[13,16]. However, because S_1 is mainly dominated by a HOMO to LUMO transition, the oscillator strength is vanishing which involves that these compounds are not fully suitable for light-emitting applications. Note also that very recently, Pollice *et al.* performed a high-throughput computational screening on a large family of substituted N-doped triangulenes showing how the breaking of the D_{3h} symmetry can conciliate the negative ΔE_{ST} and a non-zero $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ oscillator strength^[22].

On the other hand, an alternative application which would benefit from the S_1 - T_1 inversion is organic photocatalysis^[23], where the zero oscillator strength do not represent necessarily a shortcoming. Computational studies carried out by Domcke *et al.* showed the active role played by the heptazine in photoinduced water splitting entailing the formation of a heptazine-water complex in the excited state^[24].

Undoubtedly, the inversion of the singlet-triplet energy order could potentially lead to a new pathway to further improve the efficiency of OLEDs, in which the triplet harvesting is now driven by a down-conversion process. However, to become of promising new class of materials for OLED applications, INVEST molecules need to exhibit together a non-vanishing oscillator strength and a narrow emission spectrum to guarantee both large enough IQEs and the requested color purity. To fulfill these conditions, we still remark three main existing issues, namely: (i) the lack of a clear and definitive picture of the structure-property relationship characterizing the inverted singlet-triplet (INVEST) systems, (ii) the scarce number of known INVEST emitters, who also exhibit a vanishing oscillator strength because of symmetry reasons and (iii) the lack of a systematic characterization of the emission profile.

Summarizing, in this article we systematically explore some INVEST molecules to gather information useful to establish design rules aimed at guiding the identification

of molecular emitters with a negative ΔE_{ST} , a non-zero oscillator strength and a narrow emission spectrum. Section 2 will describe the methodology needed to accomplish these goals, which necessarily goes beyond standard (e.g. TD-DFT) calculations, while section 3 will assess the role of the symmetry on the orbital localization and its connection with the singlet-triplet inversion. In section 4, we will present two strategies to obtain systems with a negative ΔE_{ST} and a non-zero oscillator strength: (i) one employing substituents and (ii) one encompassing the extension of the triangulene core. In sections 5 and 6, we will investigate the photophysical properties (emission spectra and (non)radiative decay rates) of the most promising designed triangulenes, to evaluate their potential applicability in OLEDs.

2 Methodology

All the molecular structures considered have been optimized at B97-3c^[25] level, and all-real frequencies found, whereas the vertical excitation energies ($S_n \leftarrow S_0$ and $T_n \leftarrow S_0$) have been computed at Configuration Interaction of Singles (CIS), Spin Component Scaling^[26] second-order approximate Coupled Cluster Singles and Doubles (SCS-CC2)^[27] level, State-Average Complete Active Space Self Consistent Field (SA-CASSCF) and Strongly Contracted N-Electron Valence 2nd-order Perturbation Theory (SC-NEVPT2)^[28-30] employing the RI-JK^[31] approximation with the def2/JK auxiliary basis set. A (8,8) active space (eight electrons in eight molecular orbitals) were used for CASSCF and NEVPT2 calculations, ensuring a good trade-off between accuracy and computational cost. 2nd-order Møller-Plesset perturbation theory (MP2) natural orbitals were used as a first guess for CASSCF calculations. All the calculations employed the def2-TZVP basis set, expected to provide negligible discrepancy with respect to larger basis set, as already observed in our previous work^[16]. SCS-CC2 calculations were performed using Turbomole 7.4^[32] package whereas the geometry optimization, frequencies, and SA-CASSCF and SC-NEVPT2 calculations were carried out with the ORCA 4.2^[33] package. The overlap between molecular orbitals ($S_{ia} = \langle \phi_i | \phi_a \rangle$) and the Tozer's diagnostic ($\Lambda = (\sum_{i,a} c_{ia}^2 S_{ia}) / \sum_{i,a} c_{ia}^2$, with c_{ia} the coefficient associated with the one-electron transition between the occupied and virtual orbitals, ϕ_i and ϕ_a , respectively) have been computed with MultiWfn 3.6^[34] (for excited state dominated by only one-electron transition the Tozer's value reduced to the orbital overlap). Note that $0 \leq \Lambda \leq 1$, where $\Lambda=1$ ($\Lambda=0$) denotes a pure Locally Excited (LE) (pure Charge-Transfer (CT)) excitation, respectively. For the rate constants calculations, the Spin-Orbit Coupling (SOC) between S_1 and T_n has been computed at S_0 geometry at TD-DFT-PBE0/def2-TZVP employing the Breit-Pauli Hamiltonian within the ZORA approximation using ORCA 4.2^[33]. The vibronic structure of the spectra has been simulated by using Q-Chem 5.4 package^[54], optimizing the S_1 geometry at TDDFT-PBE0/def2-TZVP level and refining the absolute energy at SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP level on top of the optimized geometries.

The $k_{(R)ISC}$ have been computed using MOMAP 2021b^[57-60] using the optimized geometries and frequencies computed with Gaussian16^[56], including the Duschinsky rotation. The absolute energies of the excited state and the respective differences have been computed at SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP level on top of the PBE0 optimized geometries. The solvent effect has been evaluated by optimizing the S_0 and S_1 geometry at TD-DFT-PBE0 with the def2-TZVP and def2-SVP for single and extended triangular cores, respectively, employing the Polarizable Continuum Model (PCM) with Gaussian16^[56] and refining the excited state energies with SCS-ADC(2)/def2-TZVP calculations on top of the optimized geometries employing the Conductor-like Screening Model (COSMO) in Turbomole 7.4^[32].

3 Orbital localization and impact on optical properties

3.1 Impact of the symmetry point group on the ΔE_{ST}

In symmetric compounds, the orbital localization can be systematically deduced from the symmetry point group. The Symmetry Adapted Molecular Orbitals (SAMOs) are generated as Symmetry Adapted Linear Combinations (SALCs) of p atomic orbitals (χ_i) thanks to the *projection operators* ^[35]. Considering a single p orbital per atomic center (Figure 2) as a good approximation for (nearly) planar molecular compounds, which is usually the central assumption in the Hückel method^[36-39] and tight-binding approaches^[40-42].

Figure 2: Definition of the p atomic orbitals of the triangulene systems considered in the analysis.

The approach encompasses the following steps:

- (i) Construction of the reducible representation (RR), Γ_{red} , by operating with each symmetry operator on the atomic orbitals.
- (ii) Reduction of Γ_{red} in terms of the irreducible representations (iRRs) of the point group according to equation S1.1.
- (iii) Construction of the SALCs by means of the projection operators (\hat{P}_R) according to equation S1.2.
- (iv) Generation of the SAMOs.

(v) Identification of the HOMO and LUMO by ordering the SAMOs according to their energies computed at Hückel level and filling them with the π -electrons composing the system of interest (for instance in the cyclazine case, 14 π -electrons considering 13 C atoms and one central N atom).

In order to assess the effect of the presence/absence of a symmetry element on the orbital localization, the analysis has been carried out by considering the D_{3h} point group, the highest point group to which most of INVEST triangulene compounds belong. We also investigated its subgroups C_{2v} , C_{3h} and C_{3v} to rationalize the impact of lowering the symmetry on the orbital localization and in the end on the ΔE_{ST} .

In the following section, we present only the results of the symmetry analysis, along with the possible scenarios involving the symmetry point group at issue. For the complete analysis (generation of SALCs and SAMOs) the reader can find the details at the Supporting Information (SI).

3.1.1 Point group: D_{3h}

D_{3h} is the highest order symmetry point group that can be obtained considering triangle-shape molecules. Taking as reference the structure reported in Figure 2, the reducible representation $\Gamma_{red}^{D_{3h}}$ is written as direct sum of one- (1D) and two- (2D) dimensional iRRs: $\Gamma_{red}^{D_{3h}} = a_1'' \oplus 4a_2'' \oplus 4e''$. Optical excitations are described as (active) electronic transitions between orbitals whose iRRs direct product includes the iRR of (at least one of the components of) the transition dipole moment. So far, we have identified that both S_1 and T_1 in most of the INVEST molecules are described by electronic transitions between non-degenerate HOMO and LUMO orbitals so that these orbitals belong to a_1'' and a_2'' iRRs. Taking cyclazine as an example, we will determine the SAMOs associated with the HOMO and LUMO orbitals (see the detailed derivation in supporting information).

Starting from the iRR a_1'' , the sole SALC obtained through the projection operator coincides with the SAMO having the following form: $\psi_1^{a_1''} = 1/\sqrt{6}(\chi_2 + \chi_{10} + \chi_6 - \chi_{12} - \chi_8 - \chi_4)$, thus a linear combination of the atomic orbitals centred on the atomic sites which do not lie on a symmetry element. By rendering $\psi_1^{a_1''}$ we obtain the molecular orbitals depicted in Fig. 3(a), which essentially matches with the orbital localization of the HOMO of the cyclazine, Fig.3(b):

Figure 3: (a) a_1'' -SAMO obtained by means of the projection operator; (b) HOMO of cyclazine, computed at HF/def2-TZVP level (isocontour $\sigma=0.02 e\cdot\text{Bohr}^{-3}$).

The same analysis carried out on the a_2'' iRR leads to four SALCs that result in four a_2'' -SAMOs. Among the a_2'' -SAMOs the one labelled as $\psi_3^{a_2''}$, proportional to the linear combination of the atomic orbitals written as $0.4\chi_1 - 0.01\chi_2 - 0.4\chi_3 - 0.01\chi_4 + 0.4\chi_5 - 0.01\chi_6 - 0.4\chi_7 - 0.01\chi_8 + 0.4\chi_9 - 0.01\chi_{10} - 0.4\chi_{11} - 0.01\chi_{12} + 0.16\chi_{13}$, represents the a_2'' -SAMO depicted in Figure 4(a), which is consistent with the orbital localization of the LUMO of cyclazine, Figure 4(b).

Figure 4: (a) a_2'' -SAMO obtained by means of the projection operator; (b) LUMO of cyclazine, computed at HF/def2-TZVP level (isocontour $\sigma=0.02 e\cdot\text{Bohr}^{-3}$).

As it can be seen, while the HOMO is defined by atomic orbital centered on non-adjacent atomic sites (non-bonding character), but all p atomic orbitals contribute to the LUMO instead. Among them, the ones bringing the largest weights are centered on the atomic sites on which there is no weight on the HOMO orbital ($\chi_1, \chi_3, \chi_5, \chi_7, \chi_9, \chi_{11}, \chi_{13}$), whereas a smaller contribution derives from atomic orbitals centered on the atomic sites where the HOMO weight is different than zero ($\chi_2, \chi_4, \chi_6, \chi_8, \chi_{10}, \chi_{12}$). It follows that, even though the HOMO and LUMO are mainly localized on alternating atomic sites, there is a non-negligible, yet small overlap involving the latter set of atomic orbitals ($S_{HL} = 0.509$), leading to a non-vanishing exchange interaction energy (0.168 eV) and a ΔE_{ST} of -0.225 eV and of -0.120 eV at

the SCS-CC2 and NEVPT2 levels, respectively. We note that both apolar (*i.e.* toluene) and polar solvents (*i.e.* acetonitrile) hardly affect the magnitude of the cyclazine ΔE_{ST} (see supporting information). Further decreasing the LUMO weight on $\chi_2, \chi_4, \chi_6, \chi_8, \chi_{10}, \chi_{12}$ atomic sites and forcing its localization on the remaining atomic sites would further decrease the exchange interaction leading to an even more negative ΔE_{ST} . A related example is the B-doped parent compound of cyclazine (2T-B, Figure S2), in which the nitrogen is replaced by a boron atom, for which the MOs localization is opposite with respect to the nitrogen counterpart, *i.e.* HOMO and LUMO being now represented by the a_2'' - and a_1'' -SAMOs, respectively. Starting from this compound and introducing the more electronegative N atoms on χ_1, χ_5 and χ_9 atomic sites (2T-B-3N, Figure S3), *i.e.* by concentrating the HOMO density on the atomic sites not covered by the LUMO, the exchange interaction can be reduced from 0.155 eV ($S_{HL} = 0.453$) to 0.114 eV ($S_{HL} = 0.393$) and a reduced ΔE_{ST} value from -0.280 eV to -0.454 eV and from -0.200 eV to -0.176 eV at the SCS-CC2 and NEVPT2 level, respectively. In addition, it is worth noting how this strategy leads to an increase of the S_1 and T_1 excitation energies of 2T-B-3N with respect to 2T-B (Table S4), a behavior originating from the stabilization of the HOMO orbital with respect to the LUMO thanks to the introduction of the nitrogen atoms. We also applied this strategy to N centered triangulenes, introducing the B atom on the vertices; however, it turns out into a distorted molecular structure providing a positive ΔE_{ST} (Figure S4).

The D_{3h} point group can give rise to a second scenario, in which the MOs involved in the lower-lying singlet and triplet excited states are two degenerate orbitals, either occupied or unoccupied and thus belonging to the 2D iRR. Figure 5 shows two triangulene derivatives doped with three nitrogen atoms, reported in ref. 16 both of the same dimension and both belonging to the D_{3h} point group. In the triangulene (a) (4T-a) both the HOMO and LUMO are not degenerate with an orbital localization sharing similarities with cyclazine, *i.e.* HOMO and LUMO mainly localized on alternating atomic sites, leading to a small exchange interaction of 0.147 eV computed at the CIS level, together with a negative ΔE_{ST} (-0.275 eV and -0.260 eV at SCS-CC2 and NEVPT2 level, respectively). The different positions of the nitrogen atoms in the core of the triangulene (b) (4T-b) leads to the same HOMO pattern, but the LUMO is defined by two degenerate orbitals and so S_1 and S_2 (T_1 and T_2) excited states are degenerated. In this case, a much larger exchange interaction of 0.551 eV as computed at the CIS level within a two-state model which translates in a positive and large ΔE_{ST} (0.296 eV and 0.290 eV at SCS-CC2 and NEVPT2 level, respectively).

Figure 5: HOMO and LUMO computed at HF/def2-TZVP, exchange interaction, ΔE_{ST} and oscillator strength computed at SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP of **4T-a** and **4T-b** (isocontour $\sigma=0.02 e\text{-Bohr}^{-3}$).

This larger exchange interaction energy is a consequence of the orthogonality between the degenerate LUMO orbitals which impose a spatial localization of the LUMO orbitals at atomic sites with high HOMO weights resulting in a larger orbital overlap (see Figure 5).

Moreover, whilst in the (a) case the iRRs of the HOMO and LUMO lead to a symmetry forbidden transition ($f_{osc} = 0$), in the (b) case the 2D iRR of the LUMO (e'') guarantees a f_{osc} different from zero (0.144 at SCS-CC2 level), suggesting the critical role played by the doping pattern in modulating the optical properties of these triangle-shape systems.

It is worth noting that systems with a high symmetry such as D_{3h} are prone to undergo Jahn-Teller distortions in the excited state^[43], which could release the symmetry constraints and open a radiative pathway for the excited state. However, this effect occurs when a degeneracy in the excited states is observed, which in turn encompasses a degeneracy in the molecular orbitals. By optimizing the S_1 geometry of the triangulenes in Figure 5, we observed no lowering of the symmetry in compound (a) while compound (b) reduced its symmetry to C_{2v} . The singlet-triplet gap remains almost unaffected ($\Delta E_{ST} = -0.276$ eV), with the f_{osc} still equal to zero for compound (a) whilst it remains positive for compound (b) ($\Delta E_{ST} = 0.265$ eV, see Figure S6) with a $f_{osc} = 0.096$ for S_1 .

An analogous analysis can be done for TABNA-1^[44] a MR-TADF compound reported in literature exhibiting a D_{3h} symmetry considering the ground state optimized geometry (see Figure 1). According to its high symmetry the degeneracy of the HOMO orbitals, with the LUMO non-degenerate, leads to a positive $\Delta E_{ST} = 0.167$ eV along

with a $f_{osc} = 0.189$ for the degenerate S_1 and S_2 considering vertical excitation from the ground state (Figure S7). Similarly, as for compounds 4T-b, the optimization of the S_1 results in a decrease of the symmetry to the C_{2v} point group and a lifting of the S_1 - S_2 degeneracy. We also observed an increase of (adiabatic) ΔE_{ST} to 0.248 eV and a decrease of f_{osc} to 0.164 for S_1 .

A third scenario would involve the simultaneous degeneracy of the HOMO and LUMO orbitals. This case has been recently investigated by Domcke *et al.*^[45] in a B- and N-doped triangulene composed by three benzene rings on the rim. Interestingly, S_1 and T_1 excited states belong to two different iRRs, namely A'_2 and E' , respectively. In this case a negative ΔE_{ST} was obtained, even though the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ oscillator strength remains equal to zero.

3.1.2 Point group: C_{2v}

Lowering the symmetry to the C_{2v} point group, i.e. removing the C_3 rotation axis, leads to the loss of the 2D iRRs, resulting in the absence of degeneracy. The $\Gamma_{red}^{C_{2v}}$ is reduced to the direct sum of two iRRs: $8b_2 \oplus 5a_2$. It can be noted that these two iRRs give rise to three possible direct products: $b_2 \otimes b_2 = b_1$, $a_2 \otimes a_2 = a_1$, $b_2 \otimes a_2 = b_1$, i.e. the same iRRs of the z (a_1) and x (b_1) component of the electric dipole moment. It follows that, assuming the A_1 iRR for S_0 , the two possible iRRs of S_1 are always compatible with a symmetry allowed $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition. In light of this, by lowering the symmetry to C_{2v} the two major issues encountered with the D_{3h} symmetry are solved: (i) degenerated MOs are now no longer present, and (ii) a non-zero oscillator strength is now achievable.

The application of the projection operators of a_2 (\hat{P}^{a_2}) and b_2 iRRs (\hat{P}^{b_2}) results in five and eight SALCs, respectively, which are then combined to generate five a_2 -SAMOs and eight b_2 -SAMOs. The corresponding SAMOs $\psi_3^{a_2}$ and $\psi_5^{b_2}$ patterns (see Figure S8) are consistent with the HOMO and LUMO of cyclazine. However, while displaying the same phase alternation of the atomic orbitals as the a_2'' -SAMO of the D_{3h} symmetry point group, the $\psi_5^{b_2}$ SAMO exhibits slightly different weights on the different χ_i atomic sites. This confirms that the sole change of the point group symmetry dictate a different shape of the orbitals. Substituting cyclazine on site χ_1 with a nitrogen atom, we lowered its symmetry to the C_{2v} point group and obtained the compound represented in Figure 6a (2T-2N). The orbital localization is in line with the ones of $\psi_3^{a_2}$ and $\psi_5^{b_2}$ SAMOs (see Figure S8), resulting in the alternating hole-electron pattern. The slight changes in orbitals patterns result in an increase with respect to cyclazine of the HOMO-LUMO overlap ($S_{HL} = 0.523$) and exchange energy to 0.223 eV with the ΔE_{ST} of -0.174 and -0.120 eV, at SCS-CC2 and NEVPT2 levels of theory

respectively. In addition, the symmetry lowering results in an increase in the oscillator strength close to 10^{-3} .

Figure 6: HOMO and LUMO computed at HF/def2-TZVP (isocontour $\sigma=0.02 \text{ e}\cdot\text{Bohr}^{-3}$), hole (orange)-electron (blue) difference-density plot (isocontour $\sigma=0.001 \text{ e}\cdot\text{Bohr}^{-3}$), exchange interaction, ΔE_{ST} and oscillator strength computed at SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP and NEVPT2/def2-TZVP for 2T-2N and 2T-N-B.

As for the D_{3h} structures, relying on a B-centered triangulene substituted with N atoms (2T-B-N, see Figure 6b), retaining the C_{2v} symmetry can help to further reduce the HOMO-LUMO overlap ($S_{HL} = 0.458$) and exchange interaction (0.132 eV), leading to a more negative ΔE_{ST} along with a non-zero oscillator strength (Figure 6b). Again, in this case, the 2T-B-N shows a blue-shift of the S_1 and T_1 excitation energy with respect to 2T-2N (Table S7), thanks to the stabilization of the HOMO due to the N-doping on χ_1 site.

A well-known triangulene with a C_{2v} core is the pentaazaphenalene (5AP), obtained through the introduction of nitrogen atoms on χ_4 , χ_6 , χ_8 , χ_{10} and χ_{13} atomic sites, following the enumeration of Figure 2, widely used as a building block for the synthesis of emitting conjugated polymers^[46,47] and as Near-Infrared (NIR) absorber, exploiting the spatial localization of the HOMO and LUMO and the combined effect of Electron-Donating Groups (EDGs) and Electron-Withdrawing Groups (EWGs)^[48]. The HOMO and LUMO are, in fact, mainly localized on different atomic sites, but in contrast to the triangulenes so far explored, the non-bonding character of the HOMO is no longer provided, with the electron density extended over the bonds (Figure 7). As a consequence, the HOMO and LUMO overlap ($S_{HL} = 0.562$) leads to a higher exchange interaction (0.341 eV, twice the one of cyclazine), favouring a less negative

ΔE_{ST} . The different HOMO pattern arises from the introduction of the heteroatoms on the atomic sites composing the a_2 -block of the Hückel Hamiltonian, which is now characterized by two different values of the site-energy term (α_C and α_N) and the resonance integral (β_C and β_N), which, in turn, generate a different set of eigenvectors. This can be straightforwardly observed by computing the Hückel MOs, which are consistent with the HOMO and LUMO patterns of 5AP (Figure S9). Despite of that, SCS-CC2 calculations provided a $\Delta E_{ST} = -0.233$ eV, in clear contrast to higher correlated wavefunction methods such as ADC(3)/def2-SVP, resulting in a less negative $\Delta E_{ST} = -0.072$ eV, or NEVPT2 calculations, spanning from a negative to a positive ΔE_{ST} gradually increasing the active space: -0.089 eV, 0.034 eV and 0.036 eV for a (8,8), (10,10) and (12,12) active space. This discrepancy might derive from the inclusion of the double excitations only up to the 0th order by SCS-CC2, leading to a less accurate description of the (dynamic) electron-correlation contribution and the consequence overestimation of the S_1 - T_1 inversion, suggesting that a proper validation by means of higher correlated calculations is necessary for molecules like 5AP, lying at the edge between INVEST and TADF systems.

Figure 7: HOMO and LUMO computed at HF/def2-TZVP for 5AP (isocontour $\sigma=0.02$ e·Bohr⁻³).

A further example on the importance of the heteroatoms position in determining the MOs localization is the compound DABNA-1 (Figure S10), a (nearly) C_{2v} MR-system, in which both the HOMO and LUMO are clearly extended over the bonds, leading to a large exchange interaction and a positive ΔE_{ST} .

If, on one hand, the C_{2v} symmetry prevents the presence of orbital degeneracy and allows obtaining a non-zero oscillator strength of the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition, on the other hand, the last two examples demonstrate that within this point group a negative ΔE_{ST} is not guaranteed, suggesting that the heteroatoms position has to be carefully chosen, paying attention to not (or slightly) perturb the orbital localization of the MOs. The substitution with nitrogen atoms could result in different scenarios depending on the targeted atomic sites. On one hand, substitution on a node of the HOMO orbital leads to no impact on its pattern. On the other hand, substitution on an atomic site corresponding to an anti-node leads to a decrease of the weight of the HOMO on that particular site. We observed a redistribution of the electron density towards the other atomic sites which is the consequence of the release of the symmetry constraints on

orbital localization imposed by the D_{3h} symmetry point group. The latter case is readily explained in terms of the Hückel model. By adding nitrogen (*i.e.* heteroatoms) atoms, we introduced different α and β values. The HOMO orbital spreads preferentially between identical atomic sites since they have exactly the same α values and larger β values giving us a hint on how the HOMO pattern could be affected. A similar conclusion also holds for the LUMO orbital.

Overall, a reasonable choice to minimize the impact of electron-donating atom doping on the non-bonding character of the HOMO would be inserting the heteroatoms on the atomic sites which do not contribute to the a_2 -SALC, *i.e.* the ones sitting on symmetry elements. As it can be seen in Figure 6a, the introduction of the N atom on χ_1 preserves, in fact, the non-bonding nature of the HOMO.

3.1.3 Point group: C_{3h}

As compared to D_{3h} , the C_{3h} group does not include the C_2 axis and the σ_v plane among its symmetry elements. The resulting $\Gamma_{red}^{C_{3h}}$ is reduced to give the direct sum of iRRs, $5a'' \oplus 4e''$. The symmetry analysis focused on the sole 1D iRR (a''), since it has been already confirmed that degenerate MOs are disadvantageous for the singlet-triplet inversion (see section 3.1.1). It can be firstly noted that there is only one 1D iRR, a'' , *i.e.* moving from D_{3h} to C_{3h} the iRRs a_1'' and a_2'' , associated with HOMO and LUMO, respectively, converge to the same iRR. The application of the projection operator of the a'' iRR ($\hat{P}^{a''}$) leads to five SAMOs and none of them renders the orbital localization of the HOMO and LUMO encountered with the D_{3h} and C_{2v} point groups. Interestingly, by forcing a C_{3h} symmetry for the cyclazine, the HOMO and LUMO patterns (see Figure S11) are consistent with the orbital localization dictated by the SALCs $\psi_3^{a''}$ and $\psi_4^{a''}$, in which the atomic sites on the edge are two by two characterized by the same phase (Figure 8), *i.e.* both the MOs bear a bonding character, and thus expected to enhance the orbital overlap and increase the exchange interaction.

Figure 8: Rendering of the $\psi_3^{a''}$ and $\psi_4^{a''}$.

In light of this, it is not surprising that by forcing the C_{3h} symmetry, e.g. by using substituents (2T-N-3NH₂), this orbital localization is promoted, with consequently a large HOMO-LUMO overlap ($S_{HL} = 0.687$), exchange interaction energy and positive ΔE_{ST} , as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: HOMO and LUMO computed at HF/def2-TZVP, exchange interaction and ΔE_{ST} computed at SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP and NEVPT2/def2-TZVP for 2T-N-3NH₂ (C_{3h} symmetry) (isocontour $\sigma=0.02 \text{ e-Bohr}^{-3}$).

It is worth mentioning the case of the triazacyclazine (Figure S12), in which the position of the nitrogen atoms in the core leads to a C_{3h} symmetry. Despite the increase of the bonding character of the HOMO and LUMO, inducing a $S_{HL} = 0.552$, their patterns do not change drastically from their patterns within the D_{3h} symmetry point group and do not appear to be pronounced as compared to the compound in Figure 9. However, the exchange interaction for triazacyclazine is larger than cyclazine (0.342

eV and 0.168 eV, respectively), inducing a less negative ΔE_{ST} at SCS-CC2 and NEVPT2 levels (-0.084 eV and -0.082 eV, respectively).

It is clear that a C_{3h} symmetry, due to the unfavorable orbital localization of both the HOMO and LUMO which increases the exchange interaction, can hardly promote the singlet-triplet inversion. In addition, the lower singlet excited state oscillator strength will be vanishing since the HOMO and the LUMO (the dominant expected one-electron transition involved in S_1) belongs to the same iRR while the transition dipole moments components are associated with the a'' and e' . Summarizing, compounds with a C_{3h} symmetry are not expected to be good candidates as INVEST materials for OLED applications.

3.1.4 Point group: C_{3v}

Going to the C_{3v} point group involves losing the C_2 axis and the σ_h symmetry elements. The reduction of the $\Gamma_{red}^{C_{3v}}$ gives the direct sum of iRRs: $4a_1 \oplus a_2 \oplus 4e$. As in sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.4, we focused only on the 1D representations.

Among the resulting SAMOs, the sole a_2 -SAMO ($\psi_1^{a_2}$, corresponding to the HOMO, and the third a_1 -SAMO ($\psi_3^{a_1}$), corresponding to the LUMO, show the same pattern as a_1'' -SAMO and a_2'' -SAMO of D_{3h} , respectively. It follows that the two point groups dictate the same orbital localization and thus they are expected to provide similar order of magnitude for the exchange interaction. To corroborate this statement we computed the MOs, at the HF level, exchange interaction, at the CIS level, and ΔE_{ST} with SCS-CC2 and NEVPT2 methods for a triangulene having a phosphorus atom in the center (2T-P). The introduction of a phosphorus atom within the triangulene core induces a distortion of the molecular geometry optimized at B97-3c level, leading to a C_{3v} symmetry (Figure 10). As inferred, the HOMO and LUMO patterns provided a moderately small overlap ($S_{HL} = 0.461$), small exchange interaction (0.273 eV) and a negative ΔE_{ST} at both SCS-CC2 (-0.182 eV) and NEVPT2 (-0.095 eV). Unfortunately, as for the D_{3h} , the symmetry of the HOMO and LUMO leads to a symmetry forbidden $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition. Note that the geometry optimization with higher levels of theory, namely SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP and MP2/def2-TZVPP, results in a planar structure (D_{3h}), suggesting that the bowl-shaped geometry might be a local minimum of the B97-3c method. Nevertheless, regardless of the true equilibrium geometry, these results demonstrate that a negative ΔE_{ST} is achievable even with a distorted molecular core.

Figure 10: HOMO and LUMO computed at HF/def2-TZVP, exchange interaction and ΔE_{ST} computed at SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP and NEVPT2/def2-TZVP for 2T-P compound (isocontour $\sigma=0.02 \text{ e}\cdot\text{Bohr}^{-3}$).

3.1.5 Conclusion on orbital localization

In this section, we found that a non-bonding character and strong orbital localization can be induced to both the HOMO and the LUMO orbitals when a compound belongs to the D_{3h} , a C_{2v} , or a C_{3v} symmetry point groups. Note that the HOMO (LUMO) in N (B)-centered is expected to belong to the a_1'' iRR for the D_{3h} symmetry point group and the a_2 iRR for the C_{2v} and C_{3v} symmetry point groups. Focusing on N-centered compound, the HOMO pattern is generated through the application of the projection operator associated with the a_1'' iRR for the D_{3h} symmetry point group and the a_2 iRR for the C_{2v} and C_{3v} symmetry point groups, and it is determined from a Hückel calculation as the highest occupied SAMO. The HOMO in these point groups displays nodes on some atomic sites. For these iRRs from the above-mentioned point groups, the number of characters associated with the different symmetry operators exhibiting a “-1” and “+1” values is identical. The sum over the product of these characters by the action of the projectors associated with each symmetry elements cancels out for the atomic sites laying on a symmetry element, resulting in the nodes in the HOMO (see equation S1.2 and sections 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 in the supporting information). We observed that these nodes on the HOMO only appear when the HOMO belongs to a iRR where the rotation (C_2 in D_{3h} and C_{2v} or C_3 in C_{3v}) and the reflection plane operator have opposite character sign. We evidenced here that symmetry is key in order to impose constraints on orbital localization in these triangular-shape molecules which results in a minimization of the HOMO-LUMO overlap and thus favors a small exchange interaction.

4 Design INVEST compounds with a non-zero oscillator strength

4.1 Substituent effects

Working on the substitution pattern of the core, it turned out that the only way to conciliate a negative ΔE_{ST} and a non-zero oscillator strength requires a core with a C_{2v} symmetry with substitution at atomic sites compatible with the frontier orbitals. However, even though ideal features for INVEST emitters are achieved for the sole core, from a practical point of view, polyaromatic hydrocarbons such as triangulene derivatives are prone to aggregation which causes emission quenching and likely affects ΔE_{ST} . This requires a proper choice of bulky substituents to avoid these shortcomings.

We decided to start the computationally guided molecular design by taking as reference the cyclazine core. The symmetry can be easily reduced to C_{2v} by inserting the same number of substituents on the two sides of the molecule defined by one of the σ_v planes. Figure 11 shows a possible scenario, in which the $-R_1$ and $-R_2$ substituents sit on the atomic sites with a large HOMO and LUMO weight (see Figures 3 and 4), respectively. For the sake of illustration, we selected amino and cyano groups as model electron donating (EDGs) and withdrawing groups (EWGs). We report in Table 1 the impact of either EDGs, EWGs or their combination on the optical features.

Figure 11: a) substitution pattern b) hole (orange)-electron (blue) difference density plot computed at SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP level for **2T-f**.

Table 1: Excitation energies, ΔE_{ST} , oscillator strength and CT-distance computed at SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP for the substituted cyclazine.

		S₁ [eV]	T₁ [eV]	ΔE_{ST} [eV]	f_{osc}	D_{CT} [Å]
Cyclazine	R ₁ = H, R ₂ = H	1.109	1.334	-0.225	0.00	0.001
2T-a	R ₁ = NH ₂ , R ₂ = H	0.920	1.069	-0.149	8·10 ⁻⁴	0.114
2T-b	R ₁ =H, R ₂ = NH ₂	1.684	1.907	-0.223	3·10 ⁻³	0.124
2T-c	R ₁ = H, R ₂ = CN	0.909	1.075	-0.166	4·10 ⁻⁴	0.066
2T-d	R ₁ = CN, R ₂ = H	1.397	1.590	-0.193	8·10 ⁻⁴	0.605
2T-e	R ₁ = NH ₂ , R ₂ = CN	0.681	0.796	-0.115	1·10 ⁻⁴	0.016
2T-f	R ₁ = CN, R ₂ = NH ₂	2.084	2.214	-0.130	9·10 ⁻³	0.560

Interestingly, the vertical excited state energies can be easily tuned by introducing the EDGs and EWGs in the proper position. Moving the NH₂ group (EDG) from R₁ (high HOMO weight, compound 2T-*a*) to R₂ (high LUMO weight, compound 2T-*b*) results in an increase of both S₁ and T₁ energies while ΔE_{ST} remains constant. Analogously, the excited state energies can be increased by moving the CN group (EWGs) from R₂ (compound 2T-*c*) to R₁ (compound 2T-*d*). This behaviour is in line with the destabilizing (stabilizing) effect of the EDGs (EWGs) on the energy of the frontier MOs (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Effect of the EDGs and EWGs on the HOMO and LUMO energy computed at HF/def2-TZVP level.

Moreover, the HOMO-LUMO gap can be further decreased or increased by combining EDGs and EWGs, allowing the shift of the excitation energy from the low to the high energy regions of the spectra. This is evident with 2T-*f* compound, in which the excitation energies of the lower-lying singlet and triplet excited states are drastically blue-shifted with respect to cyclazine (from 1.109 eV to 2.084 eV and from 1.334 eV to 2.214 eV for S₁ and T₁, respectively). We further mention that considering a low polarity solvent such as toluene, the ΔE_{ST} of 2T-*f* is weakly changed. In contrast, in a polar solvent, ΔE_{ST} drops by nearly 100 meV compared to vacuum due to the higher stabilization of the T₁ carrying a higher CT character. However, the commonly used host materials in OLED usually display low dielectric constant (around 3) similar to the one of the toluene likely leaving ΔE_{ST} unaffected.

Remarkably, it can be noticed that by moving the NH₂ group from a site with a high HOMO coefficient to a site with a high LUMO coefficient, the oscillator strength increases from $8 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (compound 2T-*a*) to $3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (compound 2T-*b*). Analogously, by moving the CN group from a site with a high LUMO coefficient to a site with a high HOMO coefficient, the oscillator strength increases from $4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (compound 2T-*c*) to $8 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (compound 2T-*d*). An even higher oscillator strength can be obtained by combining the EDGs and EWGs group, as shown with compound 2T-*f* in which the oscillator strength is almost two orders of magnitude increased ($f_{osc} = 9 \cdot 10^{-3}$). This

behavior can be rationalized by inspecting the hole-electron distribution by means of two descriptors: the CT delocalization volume and the CT distance. The former is defined as the integral over the whole space of the difference between the (relaxed) real space electron density of the excited state (electron) and the ground state (hole) ($\int |\Delta\rho(r)| dr$, with $\Delta\rho(r) = \rho_{ES}(r) - \rho_{GS}(r)$) and quantifies the spatial extension of the electron density reshuffling upon the excitation^[44], whereas the latter represents the distance between the barycenters of the ground and the excited state electron densities. As it can be seen, the increase of the oscillator strength is systematically accompanied by an increase of both the CT distance D_{CT} and the CT delocalization volume (Table S14), which arises from a more spatially extended excitation due to the delocalization of the HOMO and the LUMO orbitals on the EWG and an EDG, respectively. This is coherent with the definition of the transition dipole moment, i.e. $M = \langle \Psi_{ES} | \hat{\mu} | \Psi_{GS} \rangle = -e \langle \Psi_{ES} | \hat{r} | \Psi_{GS} \rangle$: the larger the spatial rearrangement of the electron density upon the excitation, the larger the hole-electron distance is and, therefore, the larger the transition dipole moment is. Even though this statement might seem in contradiction with the necessity of ensuring a good overlap between the hole and the electron to maximize the magnitude of the transition dipole moment, it is important having in mind that in these systems the hole-electron overlap is ensured by the short-range *intra*-CT that guarantees the overlap between the tail of the hole and electron wavefunctions, similarly as observed in MR-TADF emitters^[49]. The effect of the substituents is just introducing an asymmetry in the hole and electron distribution, without breaking their alternating localization, as it can be clearly seen with the difference density plots in Figure 11b and Figure S13. D_{CT} appears as a measure of how much symmetry breaking from the D_{3h} point group occurs.

Interestingly, this strategy turned out to be effective regardless of the substitution pattern employed, provided that the EDGs and the EWGs are placed on sites with a high LUMO and a high HOMO weight, respectively (Figure S14).

4.2 Extension of the triangulene core

An alternative way for decreasing the symmetry encompasses the extension of the triangulene core by merging two (or more) triangular units with the loss of the C_3 axis and thus reducing the point group from D_{3h} to either C_{2v} , C_{2h} or their subgroups. This strategy was used previously when extending DABNA-1 into v-DABNA^[50], DiKTa to DDiKTa^[51], and ICzMes₃ to DiICzMes₄^[52]. Depending on the relative orientation of the triangulene units, the emerging structures can be considered as hetero-doped derivatives of graphene nanoribbons such as zethrene and uthrene, the latter rising attention in the last years being the smallest non-planar polycyclic biradical obtained from graphene^[53].

The boron and nitrogen-doped uthrene-like structures were obtained by merging two cyclazine units (2N-uthrene) and two boron-centered triangulene units (2B-uthrene), respectively. Their ground state geometries have been optimized at the PBE0/def2-SVP level to be consistent with the following simulation of emission spectra (*vide infra*). The resulting structures belong to the C_2 point group due to the distortion caused by the steric hindrance of the hydrogen atoms, leading to a symmetry allowed $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition with an oscillator strength of $6 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ at the SCS-CC2 level for 2N-uthrene and 2B-uthrene, respectively. A more interesting aspect characterizing these compounds is that both S_1 and S_2 lie below T_1 , with a $\Delta E(S_1-T_1) = -0.089$ eV and a $\Delta E(S_2-T_1) = -0.063$ eV for 2N-uthrene and a $\Delta E(S_1-T_1) = -0.187$ eV and a $\Delta E(S_2-T_1) = -0.076$ eV for 2B-uthrene at the SCS-CC2 level. These values are confirmed by NEVPT2 calculations providing a $\Delta E(S_1-T_1) = -0.141$ eV and a $\Delta E(S_2-T_1) = -0.084$ eV for 2N-uthrene and a $\Delta E(S_1-T_1) = -0.192$ eV and a $\Delta E(S_2-T_1) = -0.025$ eV for 2B-uthrene. Indeed, this is the first case in which the singlet-triplet inversion involves two singlet excited states. From Figure 13, it can be seen that for both the compounds S_2 is also a short-range charge transfer excited state as S_1 and T_1 , an aspect that can be easily rationalized by looking at the orbitals involved in the dominant transitions defining S_2 , *i.e.* HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+1 and HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO. It can be noted that these four dimeric MOs can be easily written as linear combinations of the HOMO and LUMO of the isolated cyclazine (Figure S15), and consequently preserve the orbital pattern which guarantees the alternating localization of the hole and electron. This is further confirmed by the *one-electron* difference density plot of S_2 (Figure S16), obtained as $(\sum_i^{L,L+1} c_i^2 \varphi_i^2) - (\sum_i^{H-1,H} c_i^2 \varphi_i^2)$ with c_i the coefficients associated with a given one-electron transition describing a given excited state and φ_i the MOs, providing the same pattern as the difference density plot obtained through the ground state and excited state relaxed electron density shown in Figure 13. However, because the S_2 arises from a different electronic configuration than T_1 , the approximation $\Delta E_{ST}(CIS) \approx 2K$ is no longer valid and the inversion may be explained assuming strong correlation effects which stabilize S_2 bringing it below T_1 . Furthermore, because of the short-range CT nature of both S_1 and T_1 , solvent effects weakly affect the $\Delta E(S_1-T_1)$ of 2B-uthrene which remains largely negative (Table S18).

Contrarily, the zethrene-like structures (Figure 14), belonging to the C_{2h} point group, show positive energy gaps considering both S_1 and S_2 : $\Delta E(S_1-T_1) = 0.128$ eV and $\Delta E(S_2-T_1) = 1.647$ eV for 2N-zethrene and $\Delta E(S_1-T_1) = 0.202$ eV and $\Delta E(S_2-T_1) = 0.848$ eV for 2B-zethrene at the SCS-CC2 level. CASSCF(8,8)/NEVPT2(8,8) calculations bring the $\Delta E(S_1-T_1)$ to -0.032 eV and -0.049 and closes the S_2-T_1 gap to 0.634 eV and 0.505 eV for 2N-zethrene and 2B-zethrene, respectively. Increasing the CASSCF active space to (10,10) leads to a positive $\Delta E(S_1-T_1) = 0.018$ eV for 2N-zethrene and $\Delta E(S_1-T_1) = 0.004$ eV for 2B-zethrene, suggesting that these compounds might lie at the edge of the INVEST and TADF systems, similarly to 5AP (section 3.1.2). The discrepancy between SCS-CC2 and NEVPT2 may again originate from the treatment of the double excitations at the 0-th order by the former method. An analysis

of the CASSCF(8,8) wavefunction shows that the percentage of double and higher order excitations in S_1 and T_1 wavefunction is $> 10\%$ for the uthrene-like structures, while it is $< 8\%$ for the zethrene-like structures (see Table S15).

Overall, the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition bears a non-zero oscillator strength ($4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ for 2N-zethrene and $3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ for 2B-zethrene at SCS-CC2 and NEVPT2 level, respectively) again due to symmetry lowering upon extension of the polyaromatic core.

Figure 13: S_1 , S_2 and T_1 vertical excitation energies, oscillator strength and hole (orange)-electron (blue) difference density plots (isocontour $\sigma=0.001 \text{ e}\cdot\text{Bohr}^{-3}$) computed at SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP for the 2N-uthrene (top) and 2B-uthrene (bottom).

Figure 14: S_1 , S_2 and T_1 vertical excitation energies, oscillator strength and hole (orange)-electron (blue) difference density plots (isocontour $\sigma=0.001 \text{ e}\cdot\text{Bohr}^{-3}$) computed at SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP for the 2N-zethrene (top) and 2B-zethrene (bottom).

As for the isolated triangulenes the application in OLED devices of the extended structures would require the introduction of bulky substituents, both to preclude the aggregation in the solid state and increase the magnitude of the oscillator strength. Nevertheless, there is no doubt that these doped nanographene-like compounds deserve further investigations as materials for OLEDs with a closed-shell ground state and an inverted singlet(s)-triplet energy gap.

5 Emission spectra simulation

We further investigate the potential of INVEST materials as emitters for OLEDs by simulating the emission spectrum for the mono- and di-substituted cyclazine defined in Table 1 with the highest oscillator strength, i.e. the compounds 2T-*b*, 2T-*d* and 2T-*f*, and the two extended triangulenes, i.e. 2N-uthrene and 2B-uthrene. We further evaluate the full half width maximum (FWHM) of the different emission spectra which is the metric characterizing color purity experimentally.

The vibronic structure of the spectra has been simulated within the Franck-Condon (FC) approximation and the Herzberg-Teller (HT) approximation, where we account for the modulation of the transition dipole moment along each vibrational normal mode (see supporting information for methodological details). All the spectra have been simulated at 300 K. The resulting emission spectra has been then shifted so that the E_{00} vibronic transition ($S_1(v=0) \rightarrow S_0(v=0)$, with v the vibrational quantum number), corresponds to the $\Delta E_{S_0-S_1}$ adiabatic energy computed at SCS-CC2 level based on the TD-DFT S_1 optimized geometry.

Figure 15: Simulated emission spectra at 300K of the compounds **2T-b** (a), **2T-d** (b) and **2T-f** (c). FC spectra (blue lines) and FC + HT spectra (red lines).

In Figure 15, the FC spectra of compounds **2T-b**, **2T-d** and **2T-f** are characterized by the highest-intensity narrow band centered at the E_{00} transition, accompanied by a weaker band at lower energy arising from the vibronic progression. The Huang-Rhys (HR) factor analysis allows identifying the normal modes at 459 cm^{-1} , 1535 cm^{-1} and 279 cm^{-1} as the ones mainly involved in the vibronic coupling in **2T-b**, **2T-d** and **2T-f**, respectively. While for **2T-b** and **2T-f** these modes are low-frequency torsional and bending modes mainly involving the substituents, thus retaining unmodified the triangulene core, the **2T-d** one is associated with a high-frequency stretching of the C-C bonds, as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: visualization of the normal modes at 459 cm^{-1} ($HR=0.1927$), 1535 cm^{-1} ($HR=0.2067$) and 279 cm^{-1} ($HR=0.3615$) for **2T-b** (a), **2T-d** (b) and **2T-f** (c), respectively.

The weaker bands at lower energy for **2T-b** and **2T-f** originate from the vibronic coupling with high frequency stretching modes at 1609 cm^{-1} and 1473 cm^{-1} for **2T-b** and **2T-f** (Figure S18), respectively, which bear the highest HR-factors in this energy region (Table S17) while for **2T-d** the contribution still comes from the mode at 1535 cm^{-1} .

Table 2: FWHM of the FC and FC+HT simulated spectra and ratio in FWHM between FC+HT and FC approaches for 2T-*b*, 2T-*d*, 2T-*f*, 2N-uthrene and 2B-uthrene compounds.

FWHM	FC [cm ⁻¹]	FC+HT [cm ⁻¹]	(FC+HT)/FC
2T- <i>b</i>	1120	2100	1.9
2T- <i>d</i>	640	2280	3.6
2T- <i>f</i>	1060	1160	1.1
2N-uthrene	800	880	1.1
2B-uthrene	1840	1840	1.0

The introduction of the HT contribution leads to the systematic increase of the low-energy band intensity with respect to the main peak (red lines in Figure 15) mainly arising from high-frequency vibrational modes within the 1000-1700 cm⁻¹ frequencies window (see Figure S19), inducing an increase of the FWHM for all the compounds (see Table 2). In particular, for 2T-*d*, the lower-energy band dominated by a high-frequency mode increases its intensity equaling the one of the E₀₀ transition, leading to the largest increase of the FWHM when moving from FC to FC+HT spectra for this compound. The normal modes with the highest Herzberg-Teller contributions for each molecule coming from two stretching modes leading to a distortion of the molecular core which break the C_{2v} symmetry (Figure S20).

It is worth comparing the FWHM values obtained from the simulated spectra with those of some MR molecules recently synthesized, namely Mes₃DiKTa^[55] (FWHM=1306 cm⁻¹ in toluene), *v*-DABNA^[50] (FWHM=645 cm⁻¹ in toluene) and DABNA-1^[3] (FWHM=1048 cm⁻¹ in toluene). While the FWHM values obtained within the FC approximation are comparable to the ones of the MR-systems, with 2T-*d* reaching a value smaller than *v*-DABNA, the inclusion of the HT contribution increases the FWHM to values much larger than the reference compounds for both 2T-*b* and 2T-*d* (see Table 2). This is stressing that for these small size small emission cross section emitters, the FWHM cannot be predicted quantitatively within the FC approximation and that inevitably one has to rely on the HT approximation. Interestingly, the 2T-*f* compound presents a similar FWHM (see Table 2) that is comparable to DABNA-1 and Mes₃DiKTa making it a suitable candidate for OLED applications.

For the 2N-uthrene and 2B-uthrene, the S₀ and S₁ geometries have been optimized at the PBE0/def2-SVP level, to keep the computational affordable, while the SCS-CC2 calculations have been carried out with a def2-TZVP basis set, for the sake of accuracy. The emission spectra for the 2N-uthrene compound is shown in Figure 17a. As for the substituted triangulenes, the spectra are characterized by a high peak centered at the E₀₀ transition (1.418 eV) along with a weak shoulder at lower energies. The normal modes with the highest Huang-Rhys factor are the ones at 55 cm⁻¹ and 247 cm⁻¹, both involving a torsional motion of the molecular core, while the mode giving rise to the weaker band is a stretching motion at 1581 cm⁻¹ (Figure 18). Despite the introduction

of the Herzberg-Teller contribution which leads to an increase of the intensity of the weaker shoulder, the FWHM remains as small as 880 cm^{-1} , below the values obtained experimentally for DABNA-1 and Mes_3DiKTa . The mode providing the highest contribution to the Herzberg-Teller mechanism is a stretching mode at 1638 cm^{-1} , shown in Figure S22b. For 2B-uthrene, the FC and FC-HT spectra result in the same emission profile (Figure 17b), with the main peak centered at the E_{00} (1.041 eV). The resulting $\text{FWHM} = 1840\text{ cm}^{-1}$, larger than 2N-uthrene but still comparable to the values of some MR-systems. This is in line with the much larger S_0 relaxation energy of 2B-uthrene than 2N-uthrene (0.162 eV and 0.084 eV, respectively), along with the larger average S_0 - S_1 bond-length variation (0.015 \AA and 0.007 \AA , respectively). The normal modes with the highest HR-factors are located in the low-frequency region, i.e. 59 cm^{-1} , 104 cm^{-1} and 157 cm^{-1} involving torsional motions of the core (Figure 19 a-c). The weaker shoulder arises from high frequency modes, in particular the ones at 782 cm^{-1} and 1325 cm^{-1} (Figure 19 d-e), the latter representing the mode with the highest contribution to the HT mechanism (Figure S22 c). Note that the narrowing of the emission by extending the size of the molecular core is an effect that has already been observed with increasing the molecular size from DABNA-1 to ν -DABNA ($\text{FWHM } 1048\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 645 cm^{-1}) and recently with a new compound synthesized by Hatakeyama *et al.* called V-DABNA^[61], obtained by merging three DABNA-1 core, and reaching a $\text{FWHM} = 564\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in toluene. Indeed, when extending the size of the conjugated core, we observed that the HR factors for the high-frequency modes (often delocalized stretching modes over the entire compound) decrease compared to single triangular compounds in line with the decrease in relaxation energy associated with these modes. It follows that the extension of the molecular core represents as well a promising strategy to enhance the color purity in INVEST compounds.

Figure 17: FC (blue line) and FC-HT (red line) simulated spectra for 2N-uthrene (left) and 2B-uthrene (right).

Figure 18: visualization of the normal modes at 55 cm^{-1} ($HR = 0.590$), 247 cm^{-1} ($HR = 0.261$) and 1581 cm^{-1} ($HR = 0.152$) for **2N-uthrene**.

Figure 19: visualization of the normal modes as 59 cm^{-1} ($HR = 0.739$), 104 cm^{-1} ($HR = 1.044$), 157 cm^{-1} ($HR = 0.251$), 782 cm^{-1} ($HR = 0.230$) and 1325 cm^{-1} ($HR = 0.156$) for **2B-uthrene**.

Overall, INVEST compounds share a large number of common features with MR-TADF emitters such as a rigid structure and an alternating hole-electron localization which would suggest that the INVEST materials would also display a narrow emission spectra ensuring color purity.

6. Rate constants calculation

In this section, we finally assess the potential of these materials to harvest triplet excitons by computing the magnitude of the (R)ISC ($k_{(R)ISC}$) rate as well as the radiative decay rate k_F , for the compounds 2T-*b*, 2T-*d*, 2T-*f* and 2B-uthrene.

Starting with the cyclazine derivatives, it can be seen that the S_1 - T_1 inversion is retained considering the adiabatic energies (see Table 3). The SOC between S_1 and T_1 , $\langle \psi_{S_1} | H_{SOC} | \psi_{T_1} \rangle$ vanishes for 2T-*b*, 2T-*d* and 2T-*f*. This can be easily rationalized in terms of symmetry (see supporting information for further details) within the C_{2v} point group. The spatial part of the S_1 and T_1 excited states wavefunctions is both dominated

by a HOMO (a_2) \rightarrow LUMO (b_2) transition, leading the two excited states belonging to a b_1 iRR. Since the representations of the spin wavefunctions of the different triplet sublevels (T_1^x , T_1^y and T_1^z) correspond to the ones of the rotation $R_{x,y,z}$ namely b_2 , b_1 and a_2 , respectively, the direct product of the iRRs, $\Gamma(S_1) \otimes \Gamma(T_1) \otimes \Gamma(R_{x,y,z})$ does not contain the totally symmetric iRR, leading to a vanishing SOC. On the contrary, T_2 is dominated by HOMO (a_2) \rightarrow LUMO+1 (a_2) transition, thus bearing a a_1 symmetry, leading the direct product $\Gamma(S_1) \otimes \Gamma(T_2) = a_1$, compatible with the iRR of R_y . As a consequence, the integral $\langle S_1 | \hat{H}_{SOC} | T_2 \rangle \neq 0$. It follows that the k_{ISC} and k_{RISC} between S_1 and T_1 for 2T-*b*, 2T-*d* and 2T-*f* vanish (at the zeroth-order) while they acquire a value different than zero for the $S_1 \leftrightarrow T_2$ interconversion, suggesting that involving the higher lying T_2 states would be necessary for the harvesting of the triplet excitons. The RISC rate from T_2 to S_1 computed without accounting from vibronic effects (HT-like or reverse internal conversion from T_1 to T_n) leads to a range of values compatible with those measured experimentally for MR-TADF emitters (see Table 3). However, recently, Marian *et al.*^[62] pointed out the critical role played by a Herzberg-Teller mechanism in promoting a non-vanishing SOC for mediating an efficient S_1 - T_1 interconversion in heptazine and its derivative leading to an increase in RISC rate resulting from symmetry lowering. Furthermore, a similar mechanism likely is also expected to enhance S_1 - T_n spin interconversion.

Table 3: S_1 vertical excitation energy and oscillator strength at S_1 geometry, S_1 - S_0 , S_1 - T_1 and S_1 - T_2 adiabatic energies, S_1 - T_1 and S_1 - T_2 SOC, fluorescence rate (without and with the Herzberg-Teller contribution), ISC and RISC for S_1 - T_1 and S_1 - T_2 transitions computed at 300 K, including Duschinsky rotation of the normal modes for 2T-*b*, 2T-*d* and 2T-*f* compounds.

	2T- <i>b</i>	2T- <i>d</i>	2T- <i>f</i>
$^a S_1^{\text{eq}}$ vert. exc. [eV]	1.506	1.250	1.750
$b f_{osc}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9 \cdot 10^{-3}$
$b f_{osc}^{\text{FC+HT}}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.1
$^a \Delta E_{S_1-S_0}$ [eV]	1.533	1.287	1.808
$^a \Delta E_{S_1-T_1}$ [eV]	-0.206	-0.202	-0.132
$^a \Delta E_{S_1-T_2}$ [eV]	-0.874	-0.863	-0.721
$\text{SOC}_{S_1-T_1}$ [cm^{-1}]	0.000	0.000	0.000
$\text{SOC}_{S_1-T_2}$ [cm^{-1}]	0.010	0.020	0.032
k_F [s^{-1}]	$2.7 \cdot 10^5$	$6.0 \cdot 10^4$	$1.2 \cdot 10^6$
$k_F^{\text{FC+HT}}$ [s^{-1}]	$5.2 \cdot 10^6$	$3.2 \cdot 10^6$	$1.9 \cdot 10^7$
$k_{ISC}^{S_1 \rightarrow T_1}$ [s^{-1}]	0.000	0.000	0.000
$k_{RISC}^{T_1 \rightarrow S_1}$ [s^{-1}]	0.000	0.000	0.000
$k_{ISC}^{S_1 \rightarrow T_2}$ [s^{-1}]	0.820	1.620	0.810
$k_{RISC}^{T_2 \rightarrow S_1}$ [s^{-1}]	$5.3 \cdot 10^3$	$7.6 \cdot 10^3$	$3.6 \cdot 10^4$

^acomputed at SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP level; ^bcomputed at TDDFT-PBE0/def2-TZVP level.

We next evaluate the S_1 - S_0 fluorescence rate constants. The k_F has been calculated according to the following expression:

$$k_F = \frac{f_{osc} \Delta E^2}{1.499} \quad (1)$$

with ΔE the vertical excitation energy at S_1 geometry in cm^{-1} . In order to account for the Herzberg-Teller effect contribution on the fluorescence rate, the value of the sum $\sum_k (\partial \mu_{if} / \partial Q_{fk}) \langle v_i | Q_{fk} | v_f \rangle$ has been added to the unperturbed transition dipole moment (μ_{if}^0) (equation S2.3) and the resulting oscillator strength (f_{osc}^{FC+HT}) has been calculated according to the following expression (note that for the sake of consistency the μ_{if}^0 obtained at TD-DFT level has been considered):

$$f_{osc}^{FC+HT} = \frac{2}{3} h\nu \mu_{if}^2 \quad (2)$$

with $h\nu$ the vertical excitation energy at S_1 geometry in *hartree* and μ_{if} the new transition dipole moment including the Herzberg-Teller term in *e-bohr*. The final fluorescence rate (k_F^{FC+HT}) has been obtained applying equation 1.

From Table 3 it can be seen that the inclusion of the Herzberg-Teller effect leads to an increase of the fluorescence rate of one order of magnitude leading to fluorescence lifetimes between 50 and 300 ns.

For the extend compounds, unfortunately, the optimization of T_1 of 2N-uthrene was unsuccessful, therefore only the results associated with 2B-uthrene were reported. The calculation of (R)ISC rate for 2B-uthrene has been carried out involving both S_1 and S_2 states as potential spin interconversion channels (see Section 4.2). As it can be seen in Table 4, the inversion of the S_1 - T_1 gap is retained considering the energies of the relaxed excited states while the S_2 - T_1 one becomes positive as obtained at the SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP//TDA-DFT-PBE0/def2-SVP. The S_1 - T_2 and S_2 - T_1 SOCs are larger than S_1 - T_1 and S_2 - T_2 ones (0.329 cm^{-1} and 0.320 cm^{-1} against 0.060 cm^{-1} and 0.030 cm^{-1}). This can be easily rationalized considering that S_1 (S_2) bears the same nature as T_1 (T_2), *i.e.* a HOMO \rightarrow LUMO transition (HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+1 and HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO). Consequently, the rates associated with the RISC processes involving T_2 - S_1 and T_1 - S_2 are the highest ones. In particular, the T_1 - S_2 RISC, thanks to the high SOC and small energy gap (0.015 eV), is characterized by the highest rate ($3.9 \cdot 10^7 \text{ s}^{-1}$), suggesting that this process might outcompete the T_2 - S_1 RISC ($8.7 \cdot 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$). It follows that the harvesting of the triplet excitons would potentially entail the RISC $T_1 \rightarrow S_2$ followed by the IC $S_2 \rightarrow S_1$, with the latter process predicted to have a rate as high as $2.5 \cdot 10^{13} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Note that the current picture in conventional and MR TADF systems encompasses a $T_1 \rightarrow S_1$ conversion mediated by a vibronically assisted $T_1 \rightarrow T_n$ *up*-conversion. The case of 2B-uthrene might open a new and alternative pathway in which the harvesting of triplet excitons occurs through a RISC between almost degenerate singlet and triplet states followed by a fast down-conversion to S_1 .

Table 4: S_1 vertical excitation energy and oscillator strength at S_1 geometry, S_1-S_0 , S_1-T_1 , S_1-T_2 , S_2-T_1 and S_2-T_2 adiabatic energy difference, S_1-T_1 , S_1-T_2 , S_2-T_1 and S_2-T_2 SOC, fluorescence rate (without and with the Herzberg-Teller contribution), ISC and RISC for S_1-T_1 , S_1-T_2 , S_2-T_1 and S_2-T_2 and IC for the S_2-S_1 transitions computed at 300 K, including Duschinsky rotation of the normal modes for **2B-uthrene**.

2B-uthrene	
$^a S_1^{\text{eq}}$ vert. exc. [eV]	0.923
$^b f_{osc}$	$9 \cdot 10^{-4}$
$^b f_{osc}^{\text{FC+HT}}$	0.034
$^a \Delta E_{S_1-S_0}$ [eV]	1.041
$^a \Delta E_{S_1-T_1}$ [eV]	-0.202
$^a \Delta E_{S_1-T_2}$ [eV]	-0.497
$^a \Delta E_{S_2-T_1}$ [eV]	0.015
$^a \Delta E_{S_2-T_2}$ [eV]	-0.279
$^a \Delta E_{S_2-S_1}$ [eV]	0.218
$\text{SOC}_{S_1-T_1}$ [cm^{-1}]	0.060
$\text{SOC}_{S_1-T_2}$ [cm^{-1}]	0.329
$\text{SOC}_{S_2-T_1}$ [cm^{-1}]	0.320
$\text{SOC}_{S_2-T_2}$ [cm^{-1}]	0.030
k_F [s^{-1}]	$4.2 \cdot 10^4$
$k_F^{\text{FC+HT}}$ [s^{-1}]	$1.6 \cdot 10^6$
$k_{\text{ISC}}^{S_1 \rightarrow T_1}$ [s^{-1}]	$9.1 \cdot 10^2$
$k_{\text{RISC}}^{T_1 \rightarrow S_1}$ [s^{-1}]	$2.8 \cdot 10^4$
$k_{\text{ISC}}^{S_1 \rightarrow T_2}$ [s^{-1}]	$2.4 \cdot 10^1$
$k_{\text{RISC}}^{T_2 \rightarrow S_1}$ [s^{-1}]	$8.7 \cdot 10^6$
$k_{\text{ISC}}^{S_2 \rightarrow T_1}$ [s^{-1}]	$7.9 \cdot 10^5$
$k_{\text{RISC}}^{T_1 \rightarrow S_2}$ [s^{-1}]	$3.9 \cdot 10^7$
$k_{\text{ISC}}^{S_2 \rightarrow T_2}$ [s^{-1}]	6.0
$k_{\text{RISC}}^{T_2 \rightarrow S_2}$ [s^{-1}]	$4.2 \cdot 10^4$
$k_{\text{IC}}^{S_2 \rightarrow S_1}$ [s^{-1}]	$2.5 \cdot 10^{13}$

^acomputed at SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP level; ^bcomputed at TDDFT-PBE0/def2-TZVP level.

Overall, the inclusion of the Herzberg-Teller effect induces a systematic increase (decrease) of the fluorescence rate constant (lifetime), promoting a higher fluorescence quantum yield which can potentially outcompete the non-radiative decay process, i.e. Internal Conversion (IC), the latter expected to be negligible thanks to the rigidity of the molecules.

7 Conclusion

The systematic and detailed symmetry analysis carried out in this work has proved to provide results in line with those obtained through *ab initio* methods, suggesting that they can be used to have a first and qualitatively hint on the magnitude of the orbital overlap and the exchange interaction term.

Figure 20: summary of the design strategies and optical features (ΔE_{ST} and f_{osc}) of the compounds investigated in this article.

At this stage, it is useful to formulate and summarize the lessons learnt so far, to write down a series of rules to design an INVEST emitter:

1. The symmetry dictates the localization of the HOMO and LUMO, which in turn leads to the alternating hole-electron pattern of the INVEST compounds.
2. A non-bonding character on the HOMO and LUMO can be obtained by imposing either a D_{3h} , a C_{2v} or a C_{3v} symmetry point group to triangular-shape compounds. Moreover, it is possible to induce vanishing weights on the HOMO (LUMO) of nitrogen or phosphor (boron)-centered triangular-shape compounds. We observed that these nodes on the HOMO only appear when the HOMO belongs to a iRR where the rotation (C_2 in D_{3h} and C_{2v} or C_3 in C_{3v}) and the plane operator have opposite character sign. This is crucial in order to minimize the overlap with the LUMO and thus favors a small exchange interaction.
3. The orbital degeneracy, either involving the occupied or unoccupied MOs, increases the exchange interaction and thus it is detrimental for the S_1 - T_1 inversion.

4. The doping pattern should be carefully chosen to avoid perturbing the non-bonding orbital localization. In light of this, a good choice might be introducing the heteroatoms on the atomic sites lying on the symmetry elements (e.g. Figure 6).
5. The negative ΔE_{ST} can be achieved even with a distorted molecular structure (C_{3v}), provided that the σ_v plane is retained.
6. The S_1 and T_1 energy can be tuned through the proper choice of EDGs and EWGs, ensuring that the substitution pattern does not affect the orbital localization and a negative ΔE_{ST} is still retained (see ref 14 as well).
7. A C_{2v} point group (and subgroups), obtained either by the doping pattern, substituents or extension of the triangulene core, can promote a negative ΔE_{ST} along with a non-zero oscillator strength, keeping in mind that this condition is however not sufficient to ensure the S_1 - T_1 inversion.
8. The oscillator strength can be increased by inserting EWGs and EDGs on the positions bearing a high HOMO and LUMO density, respectively.
9. Narrow emission can be ensured for INVEST compounds with a proper choice of the EWGs and EDGs positions on triangular-shape compounds or with extended triangular-shape, uthrene-like compounds. This is due to both the short-range charge transfer nature of the S_1 state and its delocalized excited state density which lead to small HR factors for the S_0 relaxation energy associated with high-frequency stretching modes mostly responsible for the broadening of the emission spectrum. This narrowing effect is further enhanced in the emission spectrum of extended triangular-shape, uthrene-like compounds with delocalized stretching modes resulting in even smaller HR factors associated with the S_0 relaxation energy
10. In addition, the simulations of the non-radiative rates show that in the single triangulene-core compounds the RISC would suffer from the same issue observed in MR-TADF emitters, namely a very weak T_1 - S_1 RISC rate because of the (almost) identical nature of these states while T_2 and thus T_n are so high in energy that a spin-vibronic mechanism involving reverse internal conversion from T_1 to T_n becomes unlikely. Interestingly, in the extended triangulenes, the two lower-lying excited singlet (triplet) states obtained as bonding and anti-bonding combinations of the excited wavefunctions of the single triangulene cores are very close to each other opening additional pathways for RISC. Indeed, the small T_1 - S_2 gap would imply a RISC mechanism involving a first $T_1 \rightarrow S_2$ ISC followed by a fast $S_2 \rightarrow S_1$ conversion, representing a potential new paradigm of the triplet-singlet conversion in molecular systems for OLEDs applications.

The peculiar features of the INVEST compounds can certainly open the way for fostering the performances of light-emitting devices. The growing *in silico* studies, from electronic structure investigations to high-throughput screenings, demonstrate how the theoretical prediction is essential to achieve a detailed understanding of this

new family of molecules. With the first systems providing experimental evidences of a downward energy RISC process^[63], we are confident that this work can represent a further guide-line useful to create the joining link between theory and experiment to make a step forward towards the applications of these systems in the next generation of Organic Light Emitting Diodes.

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Supporting Information

Detailed symmetry analysis (generation of SALCs and SAMOs) of the four point-groups (D_{3h} , C_{2v} , C_{3h} and C_{3v}), excited state (S_1 and T_1) energies, ΔE_{ST} at SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP and NEVPT2(8,8)/def2-TZVP and molecular orbitals computed at Hartree-Fock/def2-TZVP level for the compounds mentioned in the main text, hole-electron difference density plots of the cyclazine derivatives (section 4.1), charge transfer delocalization volume, percentage of double- and higher-order excitations in S_1 and T_1 computed at CASSCF(8,8)/def2-TZVP for 2N-uthrene and 2N-zethrene, Duschinsky rotation matrices and vibrational normal modes contributing to the Herzberg-Teller mechanism for the cyclazine derivatives (section 5), derivation of the Thermal Vibration Correlation Functions (TVCF) for the radiative and non-radiative decay processes.

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